

EdiCitNet News Template

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

EdiCitNet News

Dear all,

Please share the information related to your news using this template. We will use this information to produce news on the Website.

Don't forget to share at least one picture, to make the news more inviting.

News Information

* **News Title:** Please enter here a news title (Example: City Team Meeting in Berlin; EdiCitNet Workshop in Oslo, etc.)

Feel free to be creative !!!

Text of 30 to 150 characters will be accepted

Several WP2 meetings to adapt the EdiCitNet toolbox to the needs of cities

* **Description:** Please enter here the text related to the news you are sharing. It can be a local event, meeting or other, related to Edible City Solutions (ECS) and/or EdiCitNet in your cities.

Text of 500 to 2500 characters will be accepted

In order to adapt the toolbox to the needs of cities within the project, WP2 has strengthened the collaboration with WP5 and WP3 and with City Teams of Berlin and Montevideo. The topic of the meetings was to discuss how the toolbox could assist Living Labs and FC in data collection and monitoring.

WP2 has proposed an integrative approach for LL monitoring. The main goal is to have all data automatically stored in the EdiCitNet database and have all procedures unified in one online platform: the toolbox web. Currently, WP2, 3 and 5 are closely collaborating to further develop such proposal.

We will be more than glad to arrange new meetings with all cities and partners that ask for it.

Feature Image: Please send an image that will be displayed together with the news.

The maximum file size is 1 MB

Only files of the type png,jpg,jpeg,gif,bmp are allowed

97b6c53a-3063-4048-99fa-aacaddb7835e/Captura_de_pantalla_2020-12-15_151541.png

Additional Image (Optional): You can share here an additional image that will be displayed in the news.

The maximum file size is 1 MB

Only files of the type png,jpg,jpeg,gif,bmp are allowed

Additional Image (Optional): You can share here an additional image that will be displayed in the news.

The maximum file size is 1 MB

Only files of the type png,jpg,jpeg,gif,bmp are allowed

Additional Image (Optional): You can share here an additional image that will be displayed in the news.

The maximum file size is 1 MB

Only files of the type png,jpg,jpeg,gif,bmp are allowed

Hereby I confirm we have the rights to share this picture in EdiCitNet news.

URL: Here you can share an URL related to the news like a link to a video, website, etc.

Date: Please confirm the date of the news you are sharing.

Please specify a location related to the news you are sharing. (City, Address, Venue, etc.)

500 character(s) maximum

Contact Person

* **First and last Name:** Please enter your complete name. It will be displayed as author of the news.

* **Organisation:** Please enter the name of your organisation.

* **Position:** Please indicate your position in your organisation.

* **City & Country:** Please indicate the city and country where you are contacting us from.

* **Email:** Your email will not be shown in the news, unless you explicitly indicate it below. We will use it to contact you if we have any question.

I want my Email to be displayed in the news.

- Yes
 No

Social Media

* I agree to share my news on the EdiCitNet Twitter and/or Instagram

- Yes, both of them
 No, none of them
 Only on Twitter
 Only on Instagram

Additional Comments:

500 character(s) maximum

Contact

puerta@arttic.eu